

SMA COMPOSITE BRACES APPLIED IN EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT HYBRID STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Earthquakes are natural seismic events that induce severe damage to engineering structures. Shape memory alloys (SMAs) have been showing an interesting solution to avoid structural damage due to their high dissipation capacity by phase transformations. This investigation deals with the use of composite smart braces made by SMA, glass fiber, and polymeric matrix. A three-story building subjected to ground acceleration from El Centro earthquake is evaluated. Numerical simulations are performed to evaluate the influence of SMA volume fractions and the brace's area. Results indicate a considerable improvement in the structural response, increasing the energy dissipation and decreasing the floor displacements.

KEYWORDS

Smart structures; Shape Memory Alloy; Shape Memory Alloy Composite; Earthquake

INTRODUCTION

Earthquakes are severe seismic phenomena with a great potential for destruction, usually associated with large structural damages and even deaths (DesRoches et al., 2011). Since this extreme load condition is unpredictable and unavoidable in some regions, the design of structures to resist earthquakes loads is an important engineering challenge (Mesta et al., 2023).

Hence, special devices have been investigated through recent times in order to improve building resistance capacity. The main goal is to dissipate energy and decrease the relative displacement of each floor. Viscoelastic dampers (Tong et al., 2023) and friction pendulums (Meng et al., 2022) have been proposed in the literature. An alternative and interesting approach is the application of shape memory alloys (SMAs) to explore the phenomenon known as pseudoelasticity (Vignoli et al., 2020). For pseudoelastic behavior, the SMA has an austenitic initial microstructure, which may be transformed to martensite according to the load level. When the load is removed, a reverse phase transformation occurs, from martensite to austenite, generating a hysteresis loop (Lagoudas, 2008). These solid phase transformations have a great capability to dissipate energy, which is desirable to design earthquake-resistant structures.

SMAs bars can be embedded in concrete columns with other traditional fibers, like glass and carbon fibers (Billah & Alam, 2012; Zafar & Andrawes, 2015). However, this approach is valid just for new construction and other options must be evaluated for pre-existing buildings. For n-story frames, Ozbulut & Hurlebaus (2012) indicates that adding diagonal braces results in a significant performance improvement from a structural point of view. This conclusion is also supported by Yan et al. (2013) and Vignoli et al. (2020). Hence, the SMA composite braces seem to be the one of the most promising approaches. For a detailed discussion about different designs using SMA for earthquake applications, see Fang (2022).

A three-story building subjected to ground acceleration from El Centro earthquake is investigated in the present study. First, the SMA constitutive model is presented, followed by the dynamical modeling of the equations of motion. Next, a parametric analysis of reinforced braces with SMA, glass fiber, and polymeric matrix is carried out, comparing the energy dissipation and relative displacement of each floor with the former structure without braces. At last, the main conclusions are summarized.

SHAPE MEMORY ALLOY CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

SMA applications have been widely explored in the literature (Machado & Savi, 2003; Hartl & Lagoudas, 2007; Adeodato et al. 2021; Brandão & Savi, 2022), but the SMA constitutive modeling is still a challenge (Dornelas et al., 2021). The SMA constitutive model used in this investigation is based on Brinson (1993), but with different functions for the phase transformation kinetics. The former model uses a cosine function to establish the phase transformation relations due to its smooth feature. Recently, Adeodato et al. (2022) demonstrated that the cosine function can be replaced by polynomial functions to get more efficient numerical solutions for dynamical problems.

The proposed constitutive model in this study uses simple linear equations for the martensite volume fraction kinetics. Besides, only the pseudoelasticity is modeled. The SMA constitutive equation is defined by

$$\sigma_{SMA} = \sigma_{SMA}^0 + (E_{SMA}\varepsilon_{SMA} - E_{SMA}^0\varepsilon_{SMA}^0) - \varepsilon_R(E_{SMA}\beta + E_{SMA}^0\beta_0) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where σ_{SMA} is the stress on the SMA, ε_{SMA} is the strain on the SMA, ε_R is the maximum recoverable strain for the SMA material, β is the martensite volume fraction, $E_{SMA} = E_A + \beta(E_M - E_A)$ is the SMA elastic modulus, E_A is the austenite elastic modulus and E_M is the martensite elastic modulus.

For the pseudoelasticity phenomenon, two phase transformations may occur: the forward transformation, where the microstructure is transformed from austenite to martensite, and the reverse transformation, where the martensite is transformed to austenite.

For the forward transformation ($A \rightarrow M$), $|\dot{\sigma}_{SMA}| > 0$ and $\sigma_{AMs} \leq |\sigma_{SMA}| \leq \sigma_{AMf}$, where σ_{AMs} and σ_{AMf} are the stresses that define the start and the final forward transformation, respectively. The martensite volume fraction during the forward transformation is computed by

$$\beta = \frac{(1 - \beta_0)\sigma_{SMA} + (\beta_0\sigma_{AMf} - \sigma_{AMs})}{\sigma_{AMf} - \sigma_{AMs}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

For the reverse phase transformation ($M \rightarrow A$), $|\dot{\sigma}_{SMA}| < 0$ and $\sigma_{MAf} \leq |\sigma_{SMA}| \leq \sigma_{MA s}$, where σ_{MAf} and $\sigma_{MA s}$ are the stresses of final and start of the reverse phase transformation, respectively. The martensite volume fraction for the reverse transformation is defined by

$$\beta = \frac{\sigma_{SMA} - \sigma_{MAf}}{\sigma_{MA s} - \sigma_{MAf}} \beta_0 \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

The experimental data from Adeodato et al. (2022) for temperature equal to 303K are used to validate the application of this constitutive model using the SMA properties listed in Table 1. The comparison between experimental data and the proposed model is presented in Fig. 1. The results indicate that the linear equations for the phase transformation kinetics is in agreement with the experiments and allow a more efficient numerical solution, decreasing the computational cost and keeping the modeling reliability.

Table 1: SMA properties (Adeodato et al., 2022)

ε_R	E_A [GPa]	E_M [GPa]	σ_{AMs} [MPa]	σ_{AMf} [MPa]	σ_{MA_s} [MPa]	σ_{MA_f} [MPa]
0.06	33.2	22.1	378.5	402.2	114.2	76.1

Figure 1: Experimental and analytical results for the pseudoelastic phenomenon

THREE-STORY DYNAMICS

In this section, the equations of motion are derived considering the 3-story building represented in Fig. 2. Applying Newton's second law, the equations of motion for each floor can be defined by

$$m\ddot{u}_1 + c(\dot{u}_1 - \dot{U}_g) - c(\dot{u}_2 - \dot{u}_1) + k(u_1 - U_g) - k(u_2 - u_1) + 2F_1 \cos \theta - 2F_2 \cos \theta = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$m\ddot{u}_2 + c(\dot{u}_2 - \dot{u}_1) - c(\dot{u}_3 - \dot{u}_2) + k(u_2 - u_1) - k(u_3 - u_2) + 2F_2 \cos \theta - 2F_3 \cos \theta = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$m\ddot{u}_3 + c(\dot{u}_3 - \dot{u}_2) + k(u_3 - u_2) + 2F_3 \cos \theta = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where m is the floor mass, c is the equivalent viscous damping, k is the elastic equivalent stiffness of the building columns, \ddot{u}_i , \dot{u}_i and u_i are the accelerations, velocities and displacements of the floor i , respectively, U_g is the ground displacement, F_i are the braces' forces and θ is the inclination of the brace (see Fig. 2a).

Two different types of braces are considered in this investigation: (i) made by traditional GFRP; and (ii) made by SMA composites (SMAC) also with polymeric matrix. GFRP and the matrix from the SMAC are considered linear and elastic. The force of the braces i made by GFRP can be computed as $F_i = E_{GFRP} A_i \varepsilon_i$, where E_{GFRP} is the GFRP elastic modulus, A_i is the cross-section area and ε_i is the strain. Alternatively, the forces of the braces i made by SMAC are computed by

$F_i = [\sigma_{SMA}^{(i)} V_{SMA}^{(i)} + E_m \varepsilon_i (1 - V_{SMA}^{(i)})] A_i$, where $\sigma_{SMA}^{(i)} = \sigma_{SMA}^{(i)}(\varepsilon_{SMA}^{(i)} = \varepsilon_i)$ according to Eq. 1, $V_{SMA}^{(i)}$ is the SMA volume fraction and E_m is the matrix elastic modulus.

Defining the relative displacement of each floor by $U_1 = u_1 - U_g$, $U_2 = u_2 - u_1$ and $U_3 = u_3 - u_2$, the strain can be directly obtained using the relation $\varepsilon_i = (U_i / H) \cos \theta \sin \theta$ (Vignoli et al., 2020) and the equations of motion can be rewritten in matrix form as

$$m \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \ddot{U}_1 \\ \ddot{U}_2 \\ \ddot{U}_3 \end{Bmatrix} + c \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{U}_1 \\ \dot{U}_2 \\ \dot{U}_3 \end{Bmatrix} + k \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \end{Bmatrix} + 2 \cos \theta \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} F_1 \\ F_2 \\ F_3 \end{Bmatrix} = -m \ddot{U}_g \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where \ddot{U}_g is the ground acceleration. In this study, the data from El Centro earthquake are used for the ground acceleration, as presented in Fig. 2b, and the fourth-order Runge-Kutta is applied to solve Eq. 7.

Figure 2: (a) Dynamical model for 3-story building; (b) El Centro earthquake ground acceleration

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before introducing the results, the properties of the building and braces must be defined. The building properties are (Migda & Jankowski, 2013; Caprili et al., 2021; Mirzai et al., 2021): $m = 97 \times 10^3$ kg , $k = 3.46 \times 10^6$ N/m , $c = 6.609 \times 10^4$ Ns/m , $H = 3.5$ m and $H = 6$ m . For the braces, the SMA properties are listed in Table 1 and $E_m = 3.5$ GPa (Barbero, 2018) and $E_{GFRP} = 25$ GPa (Diniz et al., 2023).

For the sake of simplicity, all the braces are assumed with the same area (i.e. $A_1 = A_2 = A_3 = A$). An important step to design smart structures is to define where to use the smart material. To deal with this, three different configurations are considered: 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP, where the braces on the first floor are made by SMAC and the other are made by GFRP; 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP, where the first braces of the first and second floors are made by SMAC and the brace of the third floor is made by GFRP; and 3 SMAC + 0 GFRP, where all the braces are made by SMAC. For the cases where the braces of more than one floor are made by SMAC, the same SMA volume fraction is assumed.

As previously pointed out, the goal of smart structures with SMA for earthquake applications is to exploit the SMA's pseudoelasticity to dissipate energy. Thus, Fig. 3 shows the total energy dissipated during the El Centro ground acceleration considering the reinforced braces with $0\text{mm}^2 \leq A \leq 500\text{mm}^2$ and $0 \leq V_{SMA} \leq 0.6$ for the three configurations. The dissipated energy, E_d , is computed numerically using the area of the graphic force-displacement for each brace.

The first important conclusion from these results is that the graphics for 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP and 3 SMAC + 0 GFRP are equal, what means that including the SMAC braces on the third floor does not influence the energy dissipation capability, indicating that these braces do not have phase transformation. Based on this observation, the configuration 3 SMAC + 0 GFRP does not offer any advantage and it is not recommended.

For 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP and 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP, the detailed views of the parametric analysis indicate the maximum dissipated energy with a black circle and an arrow, that is very similar for both. For the 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP, the best brace characteristics are $A = 280\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.49$, while

for 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP, the braces have $A = 260\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.58$. These braces are selected for further detailed analyses.

Figure 3: Parametric analysis to evaluate the dissipated energy for: (a) 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP; (b) 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP; (c) 3 SMAC + 0 GFRP

Figure 4 shows the relative displacement for each floor for the structure without reinforced braces, with 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP braces ($A = 280\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.49$) and with 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP braces ($A = 260\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.58$) and Table 2 indicates the maximum and minimum values. The

amplitude has a considerable decrease using the braces reinforces, but there is no significant difference between both braces configurations. For 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP braces, the amplitude decreases by 30.3%, 38.7%, and 41.6% for the first, second, and third floors, respectively. For 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP braces, the amplitude decreases 32.4%, 34.7%, and 39.9% for the first, second, and third floors, respectively. These results indicate that the use of 2 SMAC braces also does not seem a good advantage. To keep this investigation, the energy dissipation and phase transformation are discussed next.

Figure 4: Relative displacements time history for the structure without reinforced braces, with 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP braces ($A = 280\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.49$) and with 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP braces ($A = 260\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.58$): (a) relative displacement of the first floor, U_1 ; (b) relative displacement of the second floor, U_2 ; (c) relative displacement of the third floor, U_3

Table 2: Maximum and minimum relative displacements

	$\max(U_1)$ [m]	$\min(U_1)$ [m]	$\max(U_2)$ [m]	$\min(U_2)$ [m]	$\max(U_3)$ [m]	$\min(U_3)$ [m]
without braces	0.1724	-0.1620	0.1151	-0.1194	0.0701	-0.0831
1 SMAC + 2 GFRP $A = 280\text{mm}^2$, $V_{SMA} = 0.49$	0.1105	-0.1201	0.0712	-0.0732	0.0485	-0.0408
2 SMAC + 1 GFRP $A = 260\text{mm}^2$, $V_{SMA} = 0.58$	0.1118	-0.1166	0.0778	-0.0780	0.0499	-0.0417

The total strain energy for each brace along the time is presented in Fig. 5, where the total energy is the sum of the elastic and inelastic (due to phase transformation) parcels. For both configurations, it is

possible to realize energy dissipation for the first brace (red line), where the energy does not tend to zero when the load is removed. Apparently, the second brace of the 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP does not dissipate energy, but this point must be confirmed by the phase transformation analysis.

Figure 5: Total strain energy (elastic and dissipated) for each brace: (a) 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP with $A = 280\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.49$; (b) 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP with $A = 260\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.58$

Figures 6 and 7 introduce the martensite time history evolutions and the stress-strain curves for the left-hand braces, respectively. For the right-hand braces, results are similar, but tension and compressions are alternating. Indeed, the second braces of the configuration 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP do not have any phase transformation and the pseudoelasticity is not well explored.

Figure 6: Martensite volume fraction evolution for the braces on the first floor with the configuration 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP with $A = 280\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.49$ and for the braces on the first and second floor for the configuration 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP with $A = 260\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.58$.

Since SMAs are much more expensive than glass fiber, the configuration 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP is indicated as the best option with concern to the evaluated conditions. This way, the smart structure can be beneficiary of the SMAC capability to dissipate energy and the stiffness of GFRP. Note that SMACs are fundamental for this engineering application because SMA wires do not have enough stability without the matrix.

Figure 7: Stress-strain curves for each brace: (a) 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP with $A = 280\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.49$; (b) 2 SMAC + 1 GFRP with $A = 260\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.58$

CONCLUSIONS

This investigation deals with smart structure design. The goal is to evaluate the application of SMAC and GFRP to improve the three-story building resistance to an earthquake load. A SMA constitutive model is established using a linear relation between the martensite volume fraction and the stress, improving the computational implementation. The results indicate that SMAC braces must be used just on the first floor because the use on the other floors does not dissipate energy, since there is no phase transformation. The best configuration obtained is 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP with $A = 280\text{mm}^2$ and $V_{SMA} = 0.49$. This 1 SMAC + 2 GFRP smart reinforced structure is able to decrease the amplitude of the relative displacements for the first, second, and third floors in 30.3%, 38.7%, and 41.6%, respectively.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.

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